

RESTORATION AND CONSERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. Restoration and conservation is the process of preserving and managing changes in a cultural heritage site, maintaining its value and, if necessary, repairing it. Certain legal requirements apply to "retention". In the law, it is believed that this should be interpreted as "protection from harm" - it is protection from damage to its value, not just a material object. By object conservation, that is, absolute physical conservation can be approached, but such cases are extremely rare. Most of our heritage sites are capable of some degree of adaptation or recycling without losing their value. In fact, the change is often essential to facilitate the optimal use of the facility in order to continue receiving investment.

Key words: restoration, conservation, heritage, preservation, adaptation, architecture, fine and applied arts.

Abstrakt. Restavratsiya va Konservatsiya - madaniy meros ob'ektidagi o'zgarishlarni saqlash va boshqarish, uning qiymatini saqlab qolish va kerak bo'lganda uni ta'mirlash jarayoni. "Saqlash" uchun muayyan qonuniy talablar qo'llaniladi. Qonunda buni "zarardan himoya qilish" deb talqin qilish kerak, deb hisoblashadi - bu moddiy ob'ekt emas, balki uning qiymatiga zarar etkazishdan himoya qilishdir. Ob'ektni saqlash orqali, ya'ni mutlaq jismoniy saqlanishga yaqinlashish mumkin, ammo bunday holatlar juda kam uchraydi. Bizning meros ob'ektlarimizning aksariyati o'z qiymatini yo'qotmasdan, ma'lum darajada moslashish yoki qayta ishlashga qodir. Darhaqiqat, o'zgartirish ko'pincha investitsiyalarni olishni davom ettirish uchun ob'ektdan optimal foydalanishni osonlashtirish uchun zarurdir.

Kalit so'zlar: restavratsiya, konservatsiya, meros, saqlash, moslashtirish, arxitektura, tasviriy va amaliy san'at.

Аннотация. Реставрация и консервация — это процесс сохранения и управления изменениями объекта культурного наследия, поддержания его ценности и, при необходимости, его восстановления. К «охране» применяются определенные юридические требования. В законе считается, что это следует трактовать как «защиту от вреда» — это защита от повреждения его ценности, а не только материального объекта. К консервации объектов, то есть к абсолютной физической консервации, можно подойти, но такие случаи крайне редки. Большинство объектов нашего наследия можно в той или иной степени адаптировать или переработать без потери своей ценности. Фактически, изменения часто необходимы для обеспечения оптимального использования объекта и продолжения получения инвестиций.

Ключевые слова: реставрация, консервация, наследие, сохранение, адаптация, архитектура, изобразительное и прикладное искусство.

In medieval manuscripts, we see a lot of use of the term repair in urban planning systems and architecture. Consequently, we can see that when this expression was used in the past, the activities of renovation of existing buildings and construction of new buildings were not sharply separated from each other. It can be shown that such differentiation occurred only at the beginning

of the 20th century. There are two reasons for this. First, after the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, with the introduction of European methods, the experience of global renovation gradually entered Central Asia, and secondly, after the October Revolution, local architecture began to develop in a completely different direction. In the Middle Ages, architecture developed based on a certain unity, but at the beginning of the 20th century, a sharp difference appeared. For example, madrasa, mosque, minaret, caravanserai built in the early 20th century, madrasas built by Ulugbek (15th centuries), mosques built in the 9th-19th centuries, or Rabati Malik's caravan palace (12th centuries) are very important for renovation. Because there was an artistic unity in the architecture of the 9th-19th centuries. Since the 1920s, a sharp difference has emerged in the artistic expression of architecture. The architects of the new era were far away from traditional architectural artistic tools.

Samarkand. The towers of the Ulugbek Madrasa damaged by an earthquake at the beginning of the 20th century.

Uzbek construction and architecture gradually gave way to European architecture and construction methods and technology in terms of technical and methodological aspects. The introduction of wide-glazed windows, attic roofs, new building materials (metal, concrete, etc.) led to the emergence of a new trend in architecture. Imitation of western architecture began without paying enough attention to local traditions. However, the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the peoples who lived there formed the geographical and political center of the land called Movarounnahr and earlier Turon in the Middle Ages. There is a commonality at the core. Consequently, buildings in Central Asia until the 9th century were mainly made of straw and raw bricks. Because of this, most of them have fallen into ruins today and have reached us only as archeological monuments.

Citadels such as Sopollitepa, Ay Khanum and Jarkutan, which date back to the second millennium BC, are located in the Surkhandarya region and have a common connection with the monuments of Namozgohtepa in Marv oasis in Turkmenistan. Monuments dating back to the second half of the first millennium BC are located in the territory of Ancient Khorezm - today's Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm region. These are Jonboz Castle, Tuproq Castle, Ayoz Castle and others. The ruins of the Kyrgyz fortress (IX-X centuries) and in the city of Termiz can be pointed out as the most ancient architectural monument, which was restored from straw and raw brick.

Ay Khanum. III-II centuries BC. On the left is the city plan. On the right - remains of buildings

Although brick has been known in Central Asian architecture since ancient times, it was not widely used until the 9th century AD. Its main development began after the Samonide mausoleum in Bukhara (IX century). Mir Said Bahrom's mausoleum and Deggaron mosque in Karmana, Arab Ata's mausoleum in Nurabad district, Bukhara, Vobkent, Jargurgan towers, a number of mausoleums show that bright examples of Uzbekistan's architecture were created from baked bricks in the 9th-12th centuries. Since the 11th century, precision constructions, which were already known, but for some reason were not widely used until now, began to be widely used. Due to this, some of the architectural monuments of Uzbekistan that have reached us were created in the IX-XIX centuries, and the main and majestic examples were created during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, and then the Uzbek khanates. They also had a positive impact on the architectural development of Afghanistan, Iran, the Caucasus, and India. The political situation in the 16th-18th centuries led to the formation of Bukhara, Khorezm, and Kokand schools of architecture in Uzbekistan. The architecture of these three regions, while forming a unified material culture of the people, gave rise to excellent examples of regional artistry, taking into account the natural climate and historical tradition. It is important to consider this in the repair. Because these architectural schools created unique examples of architecture and practical art. Without considering it, the repair process cannot be started.

Samarkand. Shahi Zinda Necropolis. VIII - XV centuries.

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